

EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF INCOME ON CONSUMER PREFERENCES FOR DORNA SWISS EMMENTAL CHEESE

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Abstract

Income level can affect consumer behavior and its intention to buy a food product. This paper aimed to evaluate the impact of the income level on consumer behavior of Emmental type cheese from Țara Dornelor, Romania, area. A questionnaire was applied online and on site and four groups were made after data collection, in function of the income level: very low (< 1800 lei), low (1800-3000 lei), medium (3000-5000 lei), and high (> 5000 lei). The consumption characteristics (frequency, amount, price willing to pay, shop place preference) and the factors affecting the buying intention were evaluated (price, taste and aroma, aspect and texture, producer, product history, health benefits, mood, ingredients used, marketing, convenience, and nutritional value). The results showed that the income level affected significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) the consumption frequency and the price willing to pay. The price willing to pay decreased as the income level decreased, while the consumption frequency was lower for the medium income group compared to the other ones. The convenience and producer factors registered significant ($p \leq 0.05$) differences among groups. The medium-high income level groups are more aware of the ingredients used, health benefits, and product characteristics, while the low income groups are also interested in the producer and nutritional value of the Emmental cheese. These results suggest the necessity to adapt the marketing policy to the population income and/or adjust the distribution of Emmental cheese in Dorna area.

Keywords: *hard cheeses, consumer behavior, questionnaire, income level, mountain product.*

INTRODUCTION

Consumer behavior depends on a series of factors such as income level, education, gender, social class, socio-economic status. The studies performed until the date suggest that the increase in income level led to a diversification of the consumer demand for a higher variety of foods (Lusk 2019). The income level tends to determine consumer food choice, but the nutritional disorders have also a major impact in all the income levels categories (Mbogori et al. 2020; Magano et al. 2023). While underdeveloped countries face malnutrition and micronutrient deficiencies (Vorster 2010), the high income population present a high incidence of overnutrition and chronic illnesses related to diet habits (Cois and Ehrlich 2014).

A review regarding the factors affecting food choice in low and middle-income countries revealed that consumer behavior depends on the environment, namely “the spaces in which consumers interact and make decisions about what food to acquire, prepare and consume as informed by physical and economic access, quality of foods, convenience and exposure to marketing information” (Karanja et al. 2022), and also the intrinsic motivation. Steyn et al. (2011) highlighted the important role of the income level

on fast food and street food consumption and demonstrated significant differences between low, middle, and high socio-economic groups regarding the choice, price, and consumption frequency. Steptoe et al. (1995) studied consumer food choice in London and demonstrated that the differences regarding choice motivation are related to gender, age and income level.

Romanian dairy products market has great potential, especially for traditional and ecological products. The research of Ilie et al. (2021) regarding consumer choice of dairy products as affected by income revealed that Romanian people prefer traditional and ecological products even if their income level is low. The same study highlighted the importance of the sensory profile, the use of natural ingredients, and the quality of milk raw material on consumer preferences (Ilie et al. 2021). The willingness to pay was significantly affected by the income level (Ilie et al. 2021). Mohammed (2020) also showed that income has a positive significant effect on dairy product consumption in United States.

Țara Dornelor is recognized for its tradition in Emmental type cheese production since 1827 (Necula et al. 2023). This area accomplishes all the conditions required for the manufacturing of high-quality Swiss cheese: the animals are fed only with hay and pasture, the ripening time is more than 90 days, the milk must be processed in a maximum 24h from milking (McSweeney 2007). A diminishing of the agriculture sector in the Dorna area was observed compared to the period before 1989, with the main production coming from small farms or individual producers (Jujea et al. 2023). At the moment there are two small dairy plants producing Swiss Emmental type cheese, trying to keep the tradition in this area.

In this context, this paper aimed to evaluate the impact of income level on Emmental cheese type consumers' behavior in Țara Dornelor area. For this purpose, a questionnaire regarding the consumption characteristics (frequency, amount, price willing to pay, shopping place) and the factors affecting the buying intention was used.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

a. Consumer preferences questionnaire

The investigation was developed in Țara Dornelor area in 2023. A questionnaire was applied online and onsite to investigate the impact of income on Dorna Emmental cheese consumer preference. The selection criteria of the panel (268 participants) included the consumption of dairy products, and the residency or the workplace in the Dorna area. General information (gender, age, income, education, number of family members), Emmental cheese consumption characteristics (frequency, amount, price willing to pay, shop place preference), and factors affecting the buying behavior (price, taste and aroma, aspect and texture, producer, product history, health benefits, mood, ingredients used, marketing, convenience, and nutritional value) were assessed. To evaluate the impact of the factors mentioned, a 5-points likert scale was used.

b. Characteristics of the panel

The characteristics of the panes are presented in Fig. 1. The consumption of Emmental type cheese question was eliminatory. Thus, for further analysis, only 254 participants were included. The panel was grouped in function of the income, as follows:

very low income (< 1800 lei), low income (1800-3000 lei), medium income (3000-5000 lei) and high income (> 5000 lei).

Fig. 1. Characteristics of the panel

c. Statistics

The data obtained from the questionnaire was transformed into numerical data and it was processed using SPSS software (trial version). The data was processed by using ANOVA ($p \leq 0.05$) and Kruskal-Wallis test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The impact of the income level on the Dorna Emmental cheese consumption is presented in Table 1. The consumption frequency and the price willing to pay (PWP) was significantly affected ($p \leq 0.05$) by the income, while the amount and the shopping place was not significantly influenced. The very low, low, and high income groups buy Emmental

cheese once a week, while the medium income group prefers to buy it several times a year. As the income level increased, the PWP also increased from 50-75 lei/kg to 75-100 lei/kg. All the groups investigated prefer to buy mostly 100-200g of Emmental cheese from dairy stores or supermarkets. Ates and Ceylan (2010) demonstrated that there are differences regarding dairy products consumption in Turkey based on the income and education level. The authors also stated that the price is a crucial aspect of the buying intention mostly for the low income people (Ates and Ceylan 2010). Idris-Adeniyi and Busari (2019) revealed that the raise of the income level led to a decrease in cheese consumption in Nigeria and this could be explained by the replacement of this type of food with other exquisite ones for other categories.

Table 1. Influence of income on Dorna Emmental cheese consumption

Group	Very low income		Low income		Medium income		High income		ANOVA	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	F	p
Frequency										
once a week	9	56.3	27	49.1	44	36.1	26	42.6	2.63	0.05
once a month	5	31.3	17	30.9	32	26.2	17	27.9		
s. times a year	2	12.5	11	20.0	46	37.7	18	29.5		
once a year	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0		
never	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0		
Amount (g)										
don't buy	2	12.5	9	16.4	18	14.8	11	18.0	0.15	0.93
100-200	9	56.3	31	56.4	66	54.1	30	49.2		
200-500	5	31.3	14	25.5	33	27.0	17	27.9		
500-1000	0	0.0	1	1.8	5	4.1	3	4.9		
>1000	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0		
PWP (lei/kg)										
< 50	4	25.0	1	1.8	18	14.8	10	16.4	2.01	0.05
50-75	6	37.5	27	49.1	34	27.9	30	49.2		
75-100	4	25.0	22	40.0	47	38.5	14	23.0		
100-125	2	12.5	4	7.3	20	16.4	5	8.2		
> 125	0	0.0	1	1.8	3	2.5	2	3.3		
Shopping place										
food market	2	12.5	3	5.5	9	7.4	6	9.8	0.93	0.43
supermarket	5	31.3	22	40.0	27	22.1	18	29.5		
local store	0	0.0	2	3.6	0	0.0	1	1.6		
dairy store	6	37.5	21	38.2	74	60.7	29	47.5		
houses	3	18.8	6	10.9	12	9.8	7	11.5		
online	0	0.0	1	1.8	0	0.0	0	0.0		

PWP – price willing to pay

The factors influencing the buying intention of the consumers in function of the income level are presented in Table 2. Only the producer and the convenience registered significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) among the groups. For the very low and low income groups, the main factors are the ingredients, taste and aroma, producer, aspect and texture, health benefits and the nutritional values, with scores > 4 . On the other hand, the

medium and high income groups do not offer the same importance to the nutritional value and producer, the ingredients used, taste and aroma, aspect and texture and the health benefits being more important. It can be observed a decreasing trend of the price importance with the income level increase. A study in India also demonstrated the dependence of cheese consumption on income level which can be justified by the preference for value added dairy products as income increases (Shilpa Shree and Serma Saravana Pandian 2017). Caspia et al. (2005) demonstrated that the flavor and taste are the main sensory characteristics that affect Cheddar cheese consumer behavior. Furthermore, the familiarity of the product plays also an important role in the buying intention due to the fact that it reduces the uncertainty related to the product and creates an improved match between expectations and sensory profile (Torricco et al. 2019). A study regarding Parmesan consumer behavior in America demonstrated that the origin of the product affects consumer behavior (Boatto et al. 2016). It was stated that a higher socio-economic level led to an increased awareness for health aspects (Sanchez-Villegas et al. 2003). Thus it can be explained the increased interest of medium and high income groups for the health benefits compared to low income groups.

Table 2. Factors influencing Dorna Emmental cheese consumption in function of the income level

Group Factor†	Very low income		Low income		Medium income		High income		F
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Paid price	3.25	1.24	3.24	1.12	3.02	1.08	2.82	0.87	1.75
Taste and aroma	4.44	0.51	4.45	0.67	4.43	0.73	4.33	0.89	0.33
Aspect and texture	4.25	0.68	4.18	0.77	4.34	0.73	4.03	0.91	2.24
Producer	4.31	1.01	4.27	0.89	3.82	1.14	3.93	0.99	2.94*
Product history	3.75	1.24	3.95	1.13	3.60	1.17	3.52	1.07	1.58
Health benefits	4.19	1.05	4.15	1.03	4.09	1.01	4.03	0.91	0.17
Mood	3.38	1.36	3.07	1.46	3.16	1.20	2.92	0.93	0.84
Ingredients used	4.50	0.81	4.20	1.04	4.48	0.88	4.51	0.81	1.48
Marketing	3.44	1.26	3.40	1.21	3.34	1.22	3.07	1.11	1.03
Convenience	3.88	1.15	3.58	1.13	3.20	1.13	3.08	1.16	3.52*
Nutritional value	4.19	0.83	4.02	0.95	3.84	1.21	3.75	1.03	1.05

a-b - different letters indicate significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$), * significant at $p < 0.05$. † 1 - not at all, 2 - a little, 3 - neutral, 4 - much, and 5 - very much.

Kruskal-Wallis test (Table 3) indicated that the distribution is different across very low, low, medium, and high income level groups ($p \leq 0.05$) for the PWP, producer, and the convenience, while for the frequency, amount, shopping place, the price paid, taste and aroma, texture and aspect, product history, health benefits, mood, ingredients used, marketing and nutritional value the distribution was the same across the studied groups (Fig. 2).

Table 3. Kruskal-Wallis test results

Factor		F	A	PWP	SP	PP	T&A	A&T	P	PH	HB	M	IU	Ma	C	NV	
Kruskal-Wallis H test		7.47	0.36	7.33	2.47	5.12	0.35	5.64	8.76	5.76	1.27	2.89	4.33	2.92	11.87	3.23	
df		3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	
Asymp. Sig.		0.05	0.95	0.05	0.48	0.16	0.95	0.13	0.03	0.12	0.74	0.41	0.23	0.40	0.01	0.36	
Monte Carlo Sig.	Sig.	0.05	0.95	0.05	0.49	0.16	0.95	0.13	0.03	0.12	0.74	0.41	0.23	0.40	0.01	0.36	
	99% Confidence Interval	Lower Bound	0.05	0.95	0.06	0.47	0.15	0.95	0.12	0.03	0.11	0.73	0.40	0.22	0.39	0.05	0.34
		Upper Bound	0.06	0.96	0.07	0.49	0.17	0.96	0.14	0.04	0.13	0.75	0.42	0.24	0.41	0.01	0.37

F – consumption frequency, A – amount consumed, PWP – price willing to pay, SP – shopping place, PP – price paid, T&A – taste and aroma, A&T – aspect and texture, P – producer, PH – product history, M – mood, IU – ingredients used, HB – health benefits, Ma – marketing, C – convenience, NV – nutritional value, df – degree of freedom.

Fig. 2. Kruskal-Wallis test graphics

CONCLUSION

The impact of the income level in Dorna area on Emmental cheese consumer preferences was studied. Regarding the consumption characteristics, only the frequency and the price willing to pay were significantly affected ($p \leq 0.05$) by the income level. The low and high income categories reported a consumption frequency once a week, while the medium income group stated that they consume Emmental cheese several times a year. Regarding the factors influencing the buying intention, only the producer and convenience registered significant differences among different income levels groups ($p \leq 0.05$). The high and medium income groups are more interested in ingredients, taste and aroma, aspect and texture, and health benefits, while the very low and low income groups are also aware of the nutritional value and producer besides those already listed. Thus, producers should adapt their marketing campaigns taking into account the preferences of consumers and considering the target audience.

The limitations of the study include the number of panelists and the unequal distribution in function of gender, age, and income level.

AUTHOR(S) CONTRIBUTION

Conceptualization, D.N. and M.U.-I.; Data curation, M.U.-I.; Formal analysis, D.N. and M.U.-I.; Investigation, D.N. and M.U.-I.; Methodology, D.N. and M.U.-I.; Project administration, D.N.; Resources, D.N. and M.U.-I.; Software, M.U.-I.; Supervision, D.N. and M.U.-I.; Validation, D.N. and M.U.-I.; Visualization, D.N. and M.U.-I.; Roles/Writing - original draft, M.U.-I.; and Writing - review & editing, D.N. and M.U.-I.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD STATEMENT

The research was done according to the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki.

INFORMED CONSENT STATEMENT

Verbal informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study. The study was conducted according to the GDPR rules.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the results of this study are available on request from the corresponding author, [M.U.-I].

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